

STUDIES ON THE NATURE OF THE RACEMIC MODIFICATIONS OF
OPTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN THE SOLID STATE.
PART XIV. METHYL, ETHYL, PHENYL, *o*- & *p*-TOLYL
AND α - & β -NAPHTHYL CAMPHOR- β -SUL-
PHONATES (*d*- & *dl*-)

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The nature of the racemic forms of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, *o*- and *p*-tolyl, and α - and β -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonates has been studied with the aid of melting point-composition diagrams. It is found that the racemic modifications of esters, namely, methyl, ethyl, *o*-tolyl, phenyl, *p*-tolyl and α -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonates are *dl*-compounds, whereas the racemic form of β -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonate exists as a solid solution.

In this communication the nature of the racemic modifications of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, *o*- and *p*-tolyl, and α - and β -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonates has been studied. Out of the three methods described (Roozeboom, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 537; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 28, 494; Bruni, *Gazzetta*, 1900, 30, 35; Singh, B.K. *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1944, 14, 171), the one based on Roozeboom's freezing (melting) point-composition diagrams has been employed to diagnose the nature of the racemic modifications. If the diagram is composed of (i) three curves, the racemic form is a true *dl*-compound; (ii) two curves, it is a *mechanical mixture* or *conglomerate*; (iii) one curve, a *solid solution* of the optically active and opposite forms.

We have characterised the racemic form of β -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonate as a *solid solution* and the racemic forms of the rest of the substances studied as *dl*-compounds. As the diagrams are symmetrical, only one of the active forms is required for the study.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the racemic esters as well as *p*-tolyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate are new substances. Methyl, ethyl, phenyl, *o*-tolyl, α - and β -naphthyl esters of *d*-camphor- β -sulphonic acid were prepared according to Hilditch and Edmondson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 220).

The aryl esters of camphor- β -sulphonic acids (*d*- and *dl*-) were prepared by the Schöotten-Baumann reaction. Camphor- β -sulphonyl chloride (slightly in excess of one mol. proportion) was added to a solution of phenol or naphthol (one mol.) in dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10%), maintained at 85-90°, so as to keep the sulphonyl chloride in molten condition. The mixture was shaken well for 15 minutes, cooled, filtered and recrystallised from rectified spirit. *m*-Tolyl *d*-camphor- β -sulphonate could not be isolated, as it formed a gummy mass; its racemic form (m.p. 89°), however, could be prepared (Table I).

The alkyl esters were prepared by a somewhat different method. The solution of camphor- β -sulphonyl chloride (one mol.) in methyl or ethyl alcohol was added to the cooled solution of sodium alkoxide (one mol.). When the reaction was complete after 15 minutes, the mixture was poured on ice, the separated ester filtered and crystallised from the corresponding alcohol.

The physical properties and the results of analyses of different esters are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Esters of camphor- β -sulphonic acid & mol. formula.	M.P.	Crystalline form.	% Sulphur.		Remarks.	
			Found.	Calc.		
Methyl $C_{11}H_{18}SO_3$	<i>d</i> - 61°	Thin plates	12.65	13.01	A. Solubility: All the compounds are fairly soluble in ether, benzene, ethyl acetate, pyridine, chloroform, and methyl alcohol; less so in ethyl alcohol and insoluble in water.	
Ethyl $C_{12}H_{20}SO_3$	<i>dl</i> - 57°	Do	13.27	12.26		
	<i>d</i> - 47°	Do	12.36			
Phenyl $C_{16}H_{20}SO_3$	<i>dl</i> - 37°	Do	12.06	10.97		
	<i>d</i> - *38°	Rectangular prisms	10.97			
	<i>dl</i> - 53°	Prismatic needles	10.84			
<i>o</i> -Tolyl $C_{17}H_{22}SO_3$	<i>d</i> - 58°	Needles	10.67	10.46	B. Melting points: The melting point of phenyl <i>d</i> -camphor- β -sulphonate, as reported by Hilditch*, is 48°, whereas we find it to be 38°. Similarly α -naphthyl <i>d</i> -camphor- β -sulphonate melts at 115°, whereas, it was reported** to melt at 109°.	
	<i>dl</i> - 87°	Rectangular cubes	10.31			
<i>m</i> -Tolyl $C_{17}H_{22}SO_3$	<i>d</i> -	Gummy consistency		10.46		
	<i>dl</i> - 89°	Rectangular cubes	10.33			
<i>p</i> -Tolyl $C_{17}H_{22}SO_3$	<i>d</i> - 64°	Prismatic needles	10.34	10.45		
	<i>dl</i> - 62.5°	Do	10.14			
α -Naphthyl $C_{20}H_{22}SO_4$	<i>d</i> - 115°	Needles	8.84	8.94	*Hilditch (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1909, 98, 1570).	
	<i>dl</i> - 121°	Rectangular cubes	9.06			
β -Naphthyl $C_{20}H_{22}SO_4$	<i>d</i> - 100°	Rectangular plates	9.12	8.94		**Hilditch (<i>ibid.</i> , 1909, 98, 331).
	<i>dl</i> - 97°	Do	8.98			

The melting point-composition diagrams (Figs. 1 and 2) were prepared as follows. The melting points of the homogeneous mixtures consisting of known proportions of *d*- and racemic forms are plotted against the percentage composition. The tables giving the melting points of the mixtures and their compositions are omitted for the sake of economy of space.

FIG. 1

Curves I to IV refer respectively to *p*-tolyl, methyl, α -naphthyl and ethyl camphor- β -sulphonates.

FIG. 2

Curves I to III refer respectively to β -naphthyl *o*-tolyl and phenyl camphor- β -sulphonates.

DISCUSSION

Alkyl and Aryl Esters of Camphor- β -sulphonic Acids.—The melting point—composition diagrams (Figs. 1 and 2) of methyl, ethyl, phenyl, tolyl (*o*- and *p*-) and α -naphthyl esters consist, in each case, of three curves, DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L with a central maximum, R. This indicates that the racemic esters are true *dl*-compounds. The eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 , are sharp and well defined, except in the case of phenyl esters.

The *dl-d* curve of methyl esters (Fig. 1-II) is steep in the initial stages and the area under it is small, showing that the racemic ester is stable but over a small range. The *dl-d* curve of ethyl esters (Fig. 1-IV) is less steep and the area under it is smaller than that of the methyl esters. This points to the lower stability of the *dl*-ethyl ester than that of the *dl*-methyl ester.

In the case of the phenyl esters the curve, E_1RE_2 , (Fig. 2-III) is steep and the area under it is large, indicating that the racemic compound is stable and the range of stability is fair. The central portion of the curve is rounded, pointing to the dissociation of the racemic compound at its melting point to the optically active components. There are no sharp and well-defined eutectic points and the curve lying in the range from 80*d*:20*dl* to 50*d*:50*dl* is flat and continuous, indicating the racemic modification to form solid solution with its active form in that range.

The central portion of the curve of *o*-tolyl esters (Fig. 2-II) is very steep and the area under it is very large, indicating the compound to be stable and the range of stability to be considerable. The somewhat rounded form of the curve at the maximum points to the dissociation of the racemic compound at its melting point to the optically active components. The central portion of the curve in the case of *p*-tolyl esters (Fig. 1-I) is very much rounded, showing that the racemic compound dissociates at its melting point.

The central portion of the curve of α -naphthyl esters (Fig. 1-III) is steep and the area under it is large, indicating the compound to be stable and the range of its stability to be fair. The central portion of the curve is somewhat rounded, pointing to the dissociation of the racemic form at its melting point.

The melting point-composition diagram of β -naphthyl camphor- β -sulphonates (Fig. 2-1) consists of a single continuous curve, DRL, with a minimum at R, which indicates the racemic form to be a solid solution of the optically active and opposite isomers.

The authors wish to reserve the study of other similar esters of camphor- β -sulphonic acids (*d*- & *dl*-) which is in progress.

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